

QC Report - Agilent Technologies : 2 Color Gene Expression

QCMetrics InRange (7 of 11)

Date	Wednesday, August 11, 2010 - 12:07	BG Method	No Background
Image	US83403541_251897210115_S01 [1_3]	Background Detrend	On(FeatNCRRange, LoPass)
Protocol	GE2_105_Dec08 (Read Only)	Multiplicative Detrend	True
User Name	melblab	Dye Norm	Linear Lowess
Grid	US83403541_251897210115_S01_grid (from grid_file)	Linear DyeNorm Factor	0.26(Red)0.543(Green)
FE Version	10.5.1.1	Additive Error	5(Red)8(Green)

Sample(red/green)

Spot Finding of the Four Corners of the Array

Evaluate Grid

Feature	Local Background	
	Red	Green

	Red	Green	Red	Green
Non Uniform	0	0	0	0
Population	89	82	1513	270

Spatial Distribution of All Outliers on the Array

532 rows x 85 columns

FeatureNonUnif (Red or Green) = 0(0.00%)

GeneNonUnif (Red or Green) = 0 (0.000 %)

- BG NonUniform ● BG Population
- Red FeaturePopulation ● Red Feature NonUniform
- Green FeaturePopulation ● Green Feature NonUniform

Net Signal Statistics

Agilent SpikeIns:

	Red	Green
# Saturated Features	0	0
99% of Sig. Distrib.	587	596
50% of Sig. Distrib.	450	430
1% of Sig. Distrib.	291	294

Non-Control probes:

	Red	Green
# Saturated Features	0	0
99% of Sig. Distrib.	100860	33704
50% of Sig. Distrib.	518	462
1% of Sig. Distrib.	237	234

Red and Green Background Corrected Signals (Non-Control Inliers)

Features (NonCtrl) with BGSubSignals < 0: 16585 (Red); 18294 (Green)

Negative Control Stats

	Red	Green
Average Net Signals	403.83	401.06
StdDev Net Signals	10.71	7.43
Average BG Sub Signal	4.41	-0.00
StdDev BG Sub Signal	10.66	7.73

Local Bkg (inliers)

	Red	Green
Number	43507	44750
Avg	53.53	26.96
SD	2.55	1.49

Foreground Surface Fit

	Red	Green
RMS_Fit	5.38	4.85
RMS_Resid	19.07	13.99
Avg_Fit	406.00	407.85

Reproducibility: %CV for Replicated Probes

Median %CV Signal (inliers)

	Non-Control probes		Agilent SpikeIns	
	Red	Green	Red	Green
BGSubSignal	13.27	14.11	-1.00	-1.00
ProcessedSignal	3.69	4.38	-1.00	-1.00

Array Uniformity: LogRatios

Non-Control Agilent SpikeIns

	Non-Control	Agilent SpikeIns
AbsAvgLogRatio	0.14	0.19
AverageS/N	9.27	2.50

Sensitivity: Agilent SpikeIns - Ratio of Signal to Background for 2 dimmest probes

(+)E1A_r60_n11		(+)E1A_r60_a97	
(g)	(r)	(g)	(r)
1.0	1.0	1.2	1.0

Spatial Distribution of Significantly Up-Regulated and Down-Regulated Features

#Up-Regulated:2756 (Red) ; #Down-Regulated:2870 (Green)

▲ Up-Regulated □ Down-Regulated

LogRatio Versus Log Processed Signal

- Significantly down regulated
- Significantly up regulated
- Used to normalize
- Not differentially expressed

Agilent SpikeIns Signal Statistics

Probe Name	Exp	Obs	SD	S/N
(+)E1A_r60_n9	-1.00	-0.04	0.06	0.77
(+)E1A_r60_a107	-0.48	***	***	***
(+)E1A_r60_a135	-0.48	-0.32	0.06	5.20
(+)E1A_r60_n11	-0.48	-0.10	0.16	0.59
(+)E1A_r60_1	0.00	-0.01	0.05	0.11
(+)E1A_r60_a20	0.00	***	***	***
(+)E1A_r60_3	0.48	-0.34	0.16	2.09
(+)E1A_r60_a104	0.48	-0.33	0.04	8.34
(+)E1A_r60_a97	0.48	0.30	0.16	1.87
(+)E1A_r60_a22	1.00	-0.06	0.06	1.00

Evaluation Metrics for GE2_QCMT_Dec08

Metric Name	Value	UpLim	LowLim	IsMandatory
AnyColorPrntFeatNonUnif...	0.00	1.00	NA	False
absE1aObsVsExpCorr	0.00	NA	0.86	False
absE1aObsVsExpSlope	0.02	NA	0.85	False
gE1aMedCVBkSubSignal	-1.00	25.00	NA	False
gNegCtrlAveBGSubSig	0.00	10.00	-20.00	False
gNegCtrlSDevBGSubSig	7.73	15.00	NA	False
gNonCntrlMedCVBkSubSignal	14.11	25.00	NA	False
rE1aMedCVBkSubSignal	-1.00	25.00	NA	False
rNegCtrlAveBGSubSig	4.41	4.00	-20.00	False
rNegCtrlSDevBGSubSig	10.66	6.00	NA	False
rNonCntrlMedCVBkSubSignal	13.27	25.00	NA	False

◆ In Normal Range ◆ Evaluate

Agilent SpikeIns: % CV of Average BG Sub Signal

Median %CV: -1.00%(Red); -1.00%(Green)

Agilent SpikeIns: Expected LogRatio Vs Observed LogRatio

Y-Intercept = -0.113 ; Slope = 0.018 ; R² = 0.003